

RESEARCH ARTICLE

REVISED **Development and comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms for predictive atmospheric corrosion modeling**

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Abstract

Background

Industrial content and infrastructure are in constant danger from atmospheric corrosion, which affects economies globally. However, there is a lack of a consistent set of comprehensive data that completely surrounds the range of this problem in diverse climate and locations. The purpose of the research is to evaluate the factors that contribute to atmospheric corrosion and its diverse effects on materials in various environments.

Methods

By creating a comprehensive dataset by collecting and standardizing corrosion data from diverse environments and geographic regions and initially analyzing the data, it helped indicate the main parameters affecting corrosion. This guided the selection of future features for further modeling. Several machine learning algorithms were tested, such as linear regression, decisions tree, neural network, and, most especially, promising methods, for their corrosion rate prediction capabilities. These models were assessed based on their prediction's accuracy, and computational efficiency, with special attention to refining their performance through detailed feature engineering and hyperparameter adjustment.

Results

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Upon evaluating the performance of conventional predictive models, the research indicated that the machine learning approaches, especially with random forests methods of dress, were excellent in predicting corrosion rates, significantly improved upon these capabilities. By analyzing various machine learning approaches, it became clear that it was important to enhance their accuracy by selecting the best features and customizing them.

Conclusions

This work represents a significant advancement in the predictive modeling of atmospheric corrosion. It highlights the invaluable role of machine learning in this field. By integrating varied data sets and applying sophisticated machine learning techniques, it has established a foundation for ongoing research and the practical application of corrosion management strategies. The exceptional performance of ensemble methods, like random forests, signals their potential to improve prediction capabilities and guide more effective corrosion prevention measures.

Plain Language Summary

This paper addresses the issue of atmospheric corrosion, a naturally occurring phenomena that gradually deteriorates materials exposed to air over time, jeopardising industrial facilities, bridges, and buildings. One of the most significant obstacles in capturing and forecasting this type of corrosion is a lack of structured data. We collected and standardised corrosion data from several locations and environmental scenarios to create a more comprehensive and meaningful dataset to help with this.

This knowledge enabled us to study which elements contribute the most to corrosion and influence our selection of relevant data for constructing prediction models. Following that, we explored with a variety of machine learning algorithms (computer-based methods for detecting patterns in data), ranging from simple linear regression to more complicated decision trees and neural networks. Following a comparison of their accuracy and efficiency, we noticed that some approaches, particularly those that contain multiple models known as "ensemble methods," such as random forests, performed best in predicting how quickly materials would corrode.

We also found that improving these models by carefully refining the proper data inputs and changing the settings of the model allows them to provide more accurate predictions. This study not only reveals which machine learning algorithms are best suited for corrosion prediction, but it also lays the framework for better monitoring and protection of materials exposed to the atmosphere. This work promotes the overall objective of minimising material degradation and ensuring the longevity of critical infrastructure by combining data from numerous sources and employing a variety of analytical techniques.

Keywords

Atmospheric corrosion prediction, grid search, hyperparameter tuning, corrosion dataset, machine learning algorithms

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REVISED Amendments from Version 1

Following the reviewers' suggestions and comments, several changes have been introduced.

The most significant update is the inclusion of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) at the end of Subsection 3.1, accompanied by explanatory text and two tables presenting the results.

In addition, we have expanded the discussion on the data sources and processing, explained the dispersion observed in some of the most complex ML algorithms, outlined potential solutions as future works and included additional related references. We also added remarks on the comparison of computational times across the different models.

Finally, we removed a former "current address" for one of the authors, as she has returned to the affiliation where the work was originally conducted. Minor errata have been also amended.

Any further responses from the reviewers can be found at the end of the article

Nomenclature

A	Parameter obtained from least-squares method for Klimesmith's model
B	Parameter obtained from least-squares method for Klimesmith's model
b_i	Regression coefficients
C	TOW mean environmental parameter in Klimesmith's model
Cl^-	Chloride concentration
CR	Corrosion depth
D	Parameter obtained from least-squares method for Klimesmith's model
D	Corrosion depth in μm for ISO 9224 model
E	SO_2 environmental parameter in Klimesmith's model
e	Euler's number (value: 2.71828)
F	Parameter obtained from least-squares method for Klimesmith's model
G	Cl^- environmental parameter in Klimesmith's model
h	Metal-environment-specific time exponent in ISO 9224 model
H	Parameter obtained from least-squares method for Klimesmith's model
J	Parameter obtained from least-squares method for Klimesmith's model
n	Number of observations
R^2	Coefficient of Determination
R_{corr}	Corrosion rate in ISO 9224 model
RMS	Root Mean Square Error

SO_2	Sulphur dioxide concentration
t	Exposure time
T	Temperature
T_0	Mean temperature in Klimesmith model
TOW	Time of wetness
y	Dependent variable (corrosion depth)
\hat{y}_i	Predicted value for the i-th observation
\bar{y}	Mean of the actual values
y_i	Actual value for the i-th observation

1 Introduction

Steel and other metallic alloys provide excellent mechanical qualities while remaining reasonably affordable. However, they have a significant weakness: they are susceptible to corrosion. This phenomenon, defined as the progressive deterioration of materials produced by chemical, electrochemical, or other reactions with their environment, is a critical issue in a wide range of industries, including manufacturing, infrastructure, and transportation¹. Its economic impact is enormous, requiring costly repairs, maintenance, and replacements. Furthermore, corrosion can compromise the structural integrity and safety of infrastructures, posing significant risks. Understanding and preventing corrosion is, therefore, critical to assuring the durability and reliance of materials in a wide variety of applications.

Depending on the environmental conditions and the material qualities, several mechanisms of corrosion may occur, namely electrochemical corrosion², galvanic corrosion³, microbiologically influenced corrosion (MIC)⁴ and passivation⁵, demonstrating the complexity of the effect. To deeply understand these phenomena, modelling has resulted in a pivotal approach to studying and predicting corrosion behavior under different circumstances. These techniques have experienced notable advancements over the decades, bringing unique insights and tools to the field.

Initially, analytical models such as Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) played a central role. In the case of FEA, a computational method solves equations governing ion movement and electrochemical reactions, providing detailed spatial and temporal insights into corrosion processes. Studies such as the one by Izquierdo *et al.*⁶ have shown how FEA can mimic the intricate details of corrosion progression, offering a profound understanding of material degradation over time. Similarly, CFD models have been invaluable in examining how corrosive agents like oxygen and ions travel within fluids, influence corrosion rates and distribution. These models help to predict the impact of fluid dynamics on corrosion in environments like pipelines⁷ and offshore structures and compute corrosion rates and distribution. Another mechanistic approach, the phase field method, is used to simulate phase transitions and microstructural evolution in materials, providing a microstructural perspective on

corrosion processes⁸. Additionally, atomic-scale modelling, including molecular dynamics and density functional theory (DFT), offers insights into the fundamental atomic-scale processes that drive corrosion, such as adsorption, electron transfer, and surface reactions⁹.

However, mechanistic and first principles models have certain limitations that make them less practical for large-scale predictive applications. These models are highly computationally demanding, often requiring significant processing power and time to generate results. Additionally, they are not inherently predictive, meaning they are limited in their ability to forecast corrosion behavior in new scenarios without prior detailed knowledge of the specific corrosion process and material properties. Furthermore, their focus is often on microscopic scales, which may not translate well to insights applicable to large, real-world infrastructures. These models also struggle to handle large amounts of complex data, making them less suited for big data applications. Consequently, these drawbacks highlight the potential for machine learning models, which can address these challenges by offering scalable, data-driven solutions that are capable of predicting corrosion outcomes without the same level of computational or domain-specific knowledge.

Probabilistic models are strong tools to address these uncertainties inherent to corrosion processes. These models consider variability in material properties, environmental conditions, and other factors, providing a probabilistic assessment of corrosion risk and remaining service life¹⁰. The Monte Carlo simulation is a prominent example of this approach. By incorporating a range of environmental variations and material diversities, Monte Carlo simulations offer a comprehensive view of corrosion behavior, as in the model proposed by Engelhardt *et al.*¹¹. These probabilistic models have been crucial in industries where understanding and mitigating the risk of corrosion is essential for safety and economic efficiency. The main disadvantages are the computational demanding time required for more complex models¹².

In recent years, the probabilistic approach has evolved into data-driven and machine learning (ML) models, introducing a new promising approach to corrosion modelling. Leveraging extensive datasets, ML models can recognize intricate patterns related to corrosion, make accurate predictions about corrosion rates, and fine-tune strategies for prevention and mitigation. Models such as the ones from De Masi *et al.*^{13,14} have demonstrated the significant potential of unsupervised ML techniques for the implementation of corrosion patterns. This approach not only enhances the accuracy of corrosion predictions compared to previous models but also allows for real-time monitoring and adaptive maintenance strategies, which make them very suitable to forecast and enable effective corrosion control measures.

Following this line, the present work studies a set of ML algorithms for understanding and predicting corrosion processes for offshore conditions based on several environmental parameters. This work focuses specifically on atmospheric corrosion

as one of the main problems that must be understood, in order to reduce the economic impact of replacing damaged materials and extend the lifespan of structures. To achieve this, the corrosion depth suffered by steel in atmospheric conditions will be modelled based on environmental parameters¹⁵ such as temperature (T), relative humidity (RH), time of wetness (TOW), sulphur dioxide deposition rate (SO₂), chloride deposition rate (Cl⁻), and exposure time. The techniques used represent a broad range of approaches of various levels of complexity, all related to ML, to anticipate corrosion occurrences precisely under a wide variety of climate circumstances and variables. The findings of this study are offered to help design more effective corrosion prevention and mitigation strategies.

2 Methods

For the development of the ML algorithms, a work methodology divided into 7 steps was established (Figure S1 from Extended data¹⁶). The first step focused on the construction of the dataset (**Data collection**). This involved searching the literature to collect the largest amount of data related to environmental corrosion and constructing one unified dataset. The second part focused on data preprocessing (**Data preprocessing**). Then, the dataset was separated into different sub-datasets: one for training, another for validation and a final one for testing (**Data splitting**). The fourth step consisted of the development of the algorithm architecture by testing different ML algorithms (**Model development**). Additionally, conventional models were developed in parallel for later comparison (**Conventional models**). For testing the architecture of the different ML parameters, calibration was done following accuracy metrics and rebuilding the model with new model parameters (**Calibration**). Sixth, the results obtained were analysed, looking for the model with the best predictive capacity (**Analysis of results**). Finally, the model was implemented and tested, comparing its predictive capacity with conventional models (**Model implementation**).

2.1 Data collection

2.1.1 Literature search

Data was collected from various publications, including scouring academic journals, research papers, industry reports, and other publications related to corrosion. These publications cover a broad spectrum of metals and environmental conditions, making the dataset diverse and valuable. In this study, carbon steel samples were selected.

The first step was to define the parameters involved in each publication to have an overview of what kind of data can be expected, where T in degrees, RH in %, TOW in hours per year, SO₂ in mg/m²-d, Cl⁻ in mg/m²-d, rain precipitation (P) in mm of water and time in years. Data of corrosion measurements were usually in µm or µm/year, depending on whether the data represented a time series or just a single measurement after 1 year.

After that, rows with formal defects or duplicates were located and removed. As the corrosion study is centred on offshore conditions, categories C5 and CX of corrosion were inspected following ISO 12944-2 guidelines¹⁷. All the information

collected for the dataset construction and the parameters involved are detailed in Table S1 from Extended data¹⁶.

2.1.2 Construction of the dataset

For the construction of the final dataset, several datasets were first constructed considering different configurations of input parameters (T, RH, TOW, SO₂, Cl⁻, P and time), the total amount of data and the percentage of C5-CX corrosion category data of each dataset, removing the duplicates of them, showing the final configuration on Table 1. Most of the corrosion data collected refers only to the first year of corrosion, but some publications reported time series up to 12 years that were also included considering the year as an additional input. After evaluating the constructed datasets, it was found that the percentage of C5-CX corrosion data was similar in all datasets, and therefore, the dataset with the larger size (Dataset 4) was selected for the subsequent model development. Based on this dataset, T, TOW, SO₂ deposition rate, Cl⁻ deposition rate and time of exposure were considered as input parameters, while in years, the corrosion depth (CR in µm) was considered as the output parameter.

This dataset of 816 records is composed of 180 records from the MICAT project (130 record obtained from Pintos *et al.*¹⁵, 46 records from Chico *et al.*¹⁸ and 4 records from Panchenko *et al.*¹⁹), 190 records from the ISOCORRAG project (Chico *et al.*¹⁸), 395 records obtained from Cai *et al.*²⁰, 6 records from Castaño *et al.*²¹, 7 records from Hou *et al.*²², 25 records from the E-Asia projects (Table IV-3 from To *et al.*²³) and 13 records from EFC²⁴ (the data from 25, 26 and 27 in Table S1 from Extended data¹⁶ finally were not included in the final dataset).

2.2 Preprocessing

2.2.1 Data cleaning and filtering process

A comprehensive data preprocessing involving data cleaning and filtering steps was put in place. The primary target was to ensure the integrity and reliability of the dataset for subsequent analysis (removing rows with lack of data). After this, as a critical phase of this process, an analysis aimed at detecting the presence of outliers within the dataset was conducted. To achieve this, the Isolation Forest²⁸ algorithm

was used as the first step. All these steps are grouped into cleaning and filtering process.

After the data preprocessing phase (cleaning and filtering), a statistical analysis was performed consisting of an examination of statistical parameters, such as mean, standard deviation (std), and percentiles. To further explore the relationships among the model parameters, a Pearson's correlation matrix was constructed (Figure S2 from Extended data¹⁶) and an ANOVA analysis was made.

2.3 Partition of the dataset in training, validation and testing sub-datasets

2.3.1 Technique employed on the dataset partition

Dividing the dataset into training, validation, and testing sub-dataset is essential for developing robust, reliable, and generalizable ML algorithms. It supports model development, hyperparameter tuning, prevents overfitting, and allows for unbiased performance assessment. The `train_test_split`²⁹ function of the Python sklearn library was used to randomly divide the full dataset into the subsequent 2 sub-dataset. To verify that the data distribution was adequate, the algorithm was executed 100 times. In each iteration, it was verified that the subsets assigned reflected the same distribution of the time exposure years for each sub-dataset. This verification showed that each time, for each range of time exposure (1 year, 2 years, etc.), same amount of rows (80% and 20% for each time exposure) were distributed between both sub-datasets, with different row values each time (splitting randomly). The `train_test_split` function was applied to split the overall dataset into one sub-dataset containing the test data (*test dataset*) and another sub-dataset containing the training and validation data together (*training+validation dataset*), as during the model development, the training and validation dataset was divided randomly several times in training dataset and validation datasets. The *test dataset* was left untouched to test the developed models once optimized.

2.4 Model's development and their architectures

The development of the ML model was focused on an analysis of 6 different types of algorithms to evaluate which one can achieve a better fitting and predictive capacity. The application of these algorithms was in increasing order of complexity,

Table 1. Overall description of the different built datasets, indicating the input parameters, being that ones T, RH, TOW, SO₂, Cl⁻, P and time (marked with X) that contain each dataset; the total dataset size (number of rows) and the number and percentage of data corresponding to the corrosive categories C5-CX according to ISO 12944-2 guidelines.

	T	RH	TOW	SO ₂	Cl ⁻	P	time	Total size	C5-CX	% C5-CX
Dataset 1	X	X	X	X	X	X		198	27	13.64
Dataset 2	X	X	X	X	X			243	32	13.17
Dataset 3	X		X	X	X			595	67	11.26
Dataset 4	X		X	X	X		X	816	99	12.13
Dataset 5			X	X	X			662	72	10.88

starting from the simplest one and progressing to the most complex one. The objective of developing different algorithms and not just focusing on one was to avoid any assumption that could result in the development of an algorithm that was not the best one according to the means available.

2.4.1 Methods employed for definition of the architecture of each model

Multiple Linear Regression

The first algorithm analysed was multiple linear regression (MLR)³⁰. MLR is a statistical technique used to analyse the relationship between a dependent variable, in this case, CR, and two or more independent variables such as T, TOW, RH, SO₂, Cl⁻ and exposure time. The goal of this analysis was to understand the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables and to use this relationship for predicting the CR based on the environmental features.

For modelling the MLR the data must be first normalized. We chose a Min-Max normalization. Min-max normalization is a data preprocessing technique used to scale the data values in a range of 0 to 1. To apply min-max normalization to the variables, the minimum and maximum values of each variable were found and then the following formula was applied:

$$\text{Scale value} = (\text{original value} - \text{min value}) / (\text{max value} - \text{min value}). \quad (1)$$

The next step was to build a regression model by fitting the selected independent variables to the dependent variable. The equation for the regression model is the following one:

$$y = b_0 + b_1T + b_2TOW + b_3SO_2 + b_4Cl^- + b_5t, \quad (2)$$

where y is the dependent variable (CR); b_0 is the intercept; b_1 , b_2 , b_3 , b_4 and b_5 are the regression coefficients for each independent variable (environmental features); T , TOW , SO_2 , Cl^- and t are the normalized independent variables (environmental features). To remove the variance involved in building the model by using a random partition of the training data set and the validation set, the model was analysed 100 times, obtaining the average of the accuracy parameters for later comparison with the other models.

Polynomial Regression

The subsequent algorithm under investigation was polynomial regression (PR)³¹, a widely employed technique in ML designed to establish nonlinear relationships between dependent and independent variables. In this context, it focused on crafting a polynomial linear regression model tailored to predict CR. The same normalization method applied in the MLR was used. A critical decision entailed the determination of the polynomial algorithm's degree. This investigation was initiated by fitting a polynomial model of degree 2 and systematically increasing the degree to 4 to achieve an optimal fit for our dataset. For each progressive polynomial degree, the dataset was partitioned into distinct training and validation sets. The training set served for model training, while the validation set assessed the model's performance. Employing the same criteria as in the MLR context to mitigate dataset split variance, 100 distinct analyses were executed across a range of polynomial degrees.

Decision Tree Regressor

The third algorithm under investigation was the decision tree regressor (DTR)³². DTR is a hierarchical model that employs a tree-like structure to make decisions regarding specific outcomes. Each node within the tree corresponds to a decision based on a particular feature or variable. As the tree expands and branches, each decision becomes increasingly specific, ultimately culminating in a prediction concerning the outcome.

To initiate the development of a DTR model, the first step entailed dividing the data into a training set and a validation set. In this case, data normalization was not applied as the prediction is discrete despite the continuous output. The training set serves as the foundation for model construction, while the validation set assesses the model's accuracy. To further enhance the model's robustness and generalizability to new data, a cross-validation³³ technique was implemented, dividing the dataset into five parts.

Subsequently, the determination of hyperparameters for the DTR model was carried out, with a primary focus on two key hyperparameters: i) the maximum depth of the tree and ii) the minimum number of samples required to split a node (Table 2). The maximum depth of the tree dictates how deeply the tree can extend before ceasing to branch further. Conversely, the minimum number of samples necessary to split a node specifies the threshold for the minimum number of samples required within a node before it can be split. The grid search algorithm was executed 100 times to identify optimal hyperparameter values within a defined value range (Table 2).

Random Forest Regressor

The fourth algorithm analysed was random forest regressor (RFR)³⁴. In RFR, several decision trees are built, and their outputs are combined to obtain the final prediction. The number of trees used in the random forest is determined by the hyperparameter number of estimators. Three hyperparameters were tuned in the RFR model (Table 3): i) maximum depth tree, ii) number of estimators, and iii) minimum number of samples required to split an internal node. The range of values studied are listed in Table 3. The maximum depth tree controls the depth of the individual decision trees being built,

Table 2. DTR hyperparameters studied.

Hyperparameter	Value range values
Maximum depth	1–10
Minimum number of samples	10–60 (step = 10)

Table 3. RFR hyperparameters studied.

Hyperparameter	Range values studied
Maximum depth	1–20
Minimum number of samples	5–60
Number of estimators	20–120

which helps to reduce overfitting. The number of estimators hyperparameter controls the number of decision trees to be built, which can improve the model's performance. The minimum number of samples required to split internal nodes helps to prevent further splitting in some of the nodes and aids in reducing the model's computational burden. A cross-validation technique was used for finding the best hyperparameters composition. The grid search algorithm was run 100 times with training and validation datasets, split them from the main dataset randomly each time, applying a cross-validation five times per iteration to minimize the influence of training data on the model architecture.

Support Vector Regressor

The fifth algorithm analyzed was support vector regressor (SVR)³⁵. The SVR is a type of supervised ML model used in regression tasks. It is used to predict continuous output variables using input features. The goal of SVR is to find a regression function that minimizes the error between predicted values and real ones with a margin of error (epsilon).

The development of an SVR involves selecting the right kernel, C factor, gamma, and epsilon (Table 4). The kernel function transforms the input data into a higher-dimensional space, where it can be separated into different classes. The C factor is a regularization parameter that controls the trade-off between model complexity and training error. It helps in determining the amount of error allowed in the training process. A smaller C value indicates a softer margin, allowing more training data to be misclassified, while a larger C value produces a harder margin, requiring all training data to be correctly classified. Gamma is a parameter that defines the shape of the decision boundary. It controls the degree of influence of a training example on the decision boundary. A smaller gamma value results in a decision boundary with a higher curvature, whereas a larger gamma value results in a decision boundary with a lower curvature. The epsilon parameter defines the insensitive zone around the regression line, within which the model will not consider the errors. The selection of the epsilon value depends on the tolerance level for the error.

The same normalization method as for MLR and PR algorithms was applied to the data. To optimize the model performance, the hyperparameters were tuned using cross-validation techniques. In this case, the computational analysis time was too high for repeating the grid search algorithm, so it was applied 5 times to find the best hyperparameter combination. The grid search algorithm parameters are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. SVR parameters studied.

Hyperparameter	Values studied
Kernel	Radial basis function, sigmoid
C	1-10
Gamma	0.01-10
Epsilon	0.01-0.5

Multi-Layer Perceptron Regressor

The sixth and last algorithm analyzed was the multi-layer perceptron regressor (MLPR)³⁵. The MLPR neural network is a type of feedforward artificial neural network (ANN) that consists of multiple layers of perceptron (also known as nodes or artificial neurons) arranged in a series of interconnected layers. Each perceptron receives input signals, processes the information, and produces output signals that become inputs to the next layer's perceptron until the final output is produced.

The data was normalized employing the Min-Max normalization. Next, the design of the neural network architecture was carried out through a grid search algorithm applying cross-validation. The tuned hyperparameters were activation function, learning rate, alpha, solver and the number of hidden layers (Table 5). The activation function introduces non-linearity into the model. The learning rate determines how fast the model learns from the training data. The alpha value controls overfitting through L2 regularization³⁶. The solver parameter is used to specify the optimization algorithm used in the mode. Finally, the number of hidden layers determines the complexity and capacity of the neural network regressor. For this case, the computational analysis time was the highest, so the grid search algorithm was run just one time. The values studied from the search algorithm are listed in Table 5.

2.1.2 Description of the metrics employed for tuning each modelling hyperparameter

The different combinations of hyperparameters of each algorithm were evaluated using the statistical indicators of root mean square error (RMSE) and R^2 . Those hyperparameter configurations with the lowest RMSE and highest R^2 were the chosen configurations for each ML algorithm evaluated. R^2 (Equation 3) is a statistical measure that quantifies the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable (target) that can be explained by the independent variables used in the model. It offers a simple and interpretable metric to gauge how well the model captures the variability of the target.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (3)$$

RMSE (Equation 4) represents the dispersion or spread of prediction errors, which are essentially the deviations of data

Table 5. MLPR parameters studied (Lbfgs: Limited-memory Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno; Sgd: Stochastic gradient descent).

Hyperparameter	Values studied
Activation function	identity, logistic, tanh, Rectified linear unit
Learning rate	constant, adaptive, invscaling
Alpha	0.001-0.11
Solver	adam, lbfgs, sgd
Hidden layers	(10,10,10)-(20,80,30) step layer (2,10,2)

points from the regression line. In essence, RMSE provides insights into the degree of data clustering around the optimal fit line, indicating how closely the data conforms to this line.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{n}} \tag{4}$$

Here y_i is the real output value, \hat{y}_i is the predicted output value, \bar{y} is the mean output value and n is the total of rows.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Data preprocessing

The results of the outlier detection process were compared with previous research findings (Table S1 from Extended data¹⁶) that had identified and examined outliers within each specific dataset. This comparative analysis was carried out to determine whether it was appropriate to retain or exclude these identified outliers. After conducting a thorough examination and carefully comparing each row with its corresponding publication context, it was concluded to retain these outliers within the dataset since the previous publications had already identified and resolved any inconsistencies in the data. Consequently, although the Isolation Forest algorithm classified 121 data points as statistical outliers, these anomalies seemed to be artifacts stemming from the inherent complexities in the data derived from various sources and datasets.

The descriptive statistics (Table 6) revealed an interesting observation concerning the CR parameter, which represents CR in μm . At first glance, the maximum CR value (1,804.4 μm) seemed to deviate significantly from conventional statistical indicators (Q3 = 69.7 μm), suggesting it might be an outlier. However, the examination using the Isolation Forest algorithm definitively determined that this value did not meet the criteria for an outlier. This finding held true for other dataset parameters, except for temperature, where all statistical indicators consistently aligned.

A correlation analysis was performed by building a Pearson’s correlation matrix (Figure S2 from Extended data¹⁶). It was observed that there was a moderate correlation (0.4) between TOW and temperature, as well as a similar moderate correlation (0.45) between time and corrosion.

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out to assess the influence of the main environmental parameters—temperature (T), time of wetness (TOW), sulfur dioxide concentration (SO₂), and chloride deposition (Cl)—on the corrosion rate (CR). Time was avoided from the analysis, being obvious that under the same environmental conditions, the greater the number of years, the greater the corrosion

Table 7 summarizes the environmental levels and the corresponding number of samples considered for each factor.

Table 6. Summary of descriptive statistics of the full dataset (dataset 4) used for model development.

Index	Temperature (°C)	TOW (h/year)	SO ₂ (mg/m ² -d)	Cl ⁻ (mg/m ² -d)	time (years)	CR (μm)
count	816.00	816.00	816.00	816.00	816.00	816.00
mean	13.93	3,862.11	21.54	32.52	1.95	64.74
std	7.19	1,414.76	28.10	82.70	2.03	98.26
min	-3.10	26.28	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
Q1	7.28	3,055.05	4.20	1.50	1.00	22.98
Q2	13.34	3,766.80	11.00	9.00	1.00	37.10
Q3	18.02	4,857.53	26.00	30.20	2.00	69.70
max	29.30	8,760.00	171.68	1,300.00	12.00	1,804.40

Table 7. Environmental parameters and levels employed in the ANOVA analysis.

T_Lvl	T_Sampl	TOW_Lvl	TOW_Sampl	SO2_Lvl	SO2_Sampl	Cl_Lvl	Cl_Sampl
1	211	2	3	0	276	0	210
2	223	3	118	1	300	1	333
3	382	4	600	2	155	2	239
-	-	5	95	3	53	3	29
-	-	-	-	4	32	4	5

The temperature variable was divided into three levels, considering their quartiles as the limit of each level. For the rest of the environmental parameters, the levels were grouped following ISO 9223:2012³⁷. The time of wetness (TOW) included five levels, with a higher number of observations at levels 3 and 4 (118 and 600 samples, respectively). For the SO₂ deposition and the chloride deposition (Cl), five exposure levels were defined, the majority of which corresponded to levels 1 and 2 (300 and 333 samples for SO₂; 239 and 210 samples for Cl, respectively).

The ANOVA results (Table 8) reveal that both SO₂ concentration and Cl deposition exhibit a statistically significant effect on the corrosion rate, with F-values of 41.028 and 46.683 and p-values < 0.001, respectively. These findings indicate that atmospheric contamination and marine aerosol exposure are the dominant factors controlling the corrosion process in the studied environment. The TOW also shows a significant influence (F = 9.09, p < 0.001), emphasizing the role of moisture availability in promoting electrochemical activity on metal surfaces. Conversely, temperature shows a relatively weak correlation with the corrosion rate (F = 1.55, p = 0.21), suggesting that within the observed range, thermal variation is not the limiting factor for corrosion kinetics.

Overall, the statistical analysis confirms that chloride and sulfur dioxide deposition are the most critical environmental parameters determining the corrosion intensity, consistent with trends reported in previous studies²⁰ on marine and industrial atmospheres.

Table 8. Statistical analysis of results.

Factor	Sum_sq	df	Mean_sq	F_value	p_value
T_lvl	29951.656	2	14975.828	1.553	0.212
TOW_lvl	255754.964	3	85251.655	9.092	0.000
SO2_lvl	1324413.508	4	331103.377	41.028	0.000
Cl_lvl	1472792.915	4	368198.229	46.683	0.000

3.2 Evaluation of the developed models

3.2.1 Model architectures

The models were developed sequentially in increasing complexity. The metrics for comparing the different models among them were R² and RMSE. The first model that was built was the MLR. The regression coefficients were b₀ = -0.0809175; b₁ = 0.0945785; b₂ = 0.153686; b₃ = 0.287786; b₄ = 0.56445; b₅ = 0.276023. After building the model, an inverse normalization was applied for obtaining absolute errors. The accuracy of the MLR based on the regression coefficients obtained is described in Table 9.

For the PR algorithm, first the grade of polynomial regression that fits better the model was evaluated. Grades from 2 to 4 were considered for development of the PR model architecture. Figure S3 from Extended data¹⁶ shows how increasing the polynomial degree increases the RMSE in the validation dataset while remaining relatively constant in the training dataset. This is probably due to data overfitting to the training dataset at higher polynomial grades, implying a better model fit to the training dataset but less predictive power once applied to the validation dataset, resulting in such high RMSE values. Therefore, the best predictive configuration is obtained for a polynomial grade 2. Table 9 describes the accuracy metrics obtained in the PR model with grade 2 as a fixed hyperparameter. Comparing with MLR validation (R² = 0.47 and RMSE of 58), the accuracy metrics of the PR are better (R² = 0.61 and RMSE 46) which is expected as PR models can capture better non-linear behaviour.

The best fit values obtained from the gridsearch algorithm for developing the DTR model are listed in Table 10. The results indicate that the optimal maximum depth of the tree is 8 and the minimum number of samples evaluated in each node are 10. For deciding which hyperparameter values must be adopted, the gridsearch algorithm was launched 100 times and the mode of the hyperparameter values was chosen.

The DTR model was built with the obtained optimal hyperparameters. The accuracy metrics of the model are listed in Table 9. When compared to the PR model, the DTR model

Table 9. Summary of model architectures development.

Model	R ² training	R ² validation	RMSE training	RMSE validation	Data normalized	Number of hyperparameter evaluated
MLR	0.50	0.47	51	58	yes	0
PR	0.65	0.61	43	46	yes	1
DTR	0.85	0.43	29	45	no	2
RFR	0.89	0.70	23	36	no	3
SVR	0.79	0.72	33	39	yes	4
MLPR	0.78	0.76	31	41	yes	6

Table 10. Best fit values of the hyperparameters adjusted for the decision tree regression (DTR) model.

Hyperparameter	Best fit value
Maximum depth	8
Minimum number of samples	10

fitted the training data better with a R^2 of 0.85 (compared with a R^2 of 0.65 for the PR model). However, the predictive capability of the DTR model was worse than that of the PR model, as evidenced by a R^2 of only 0.43 when applied to the validation data. This behaviour is expected for DTR models because these tend to overfit to the training data, with a consequent reduction in the predictive capability when applied to a different dataset (e.g., when applied to the validation dataset)³⁸.

In the case of the RFR algorithm, three hyperparameters were studied. The RFR algorithm is composed of several decision trees, therefore two of the adjusted hyperparameters were the same as for the DTR model (maximum tree depth and minimum number of samples evaluated in each node). The additional hyperparameter in comparison with a single decision tree was the number of estimators (i.e., the number of decision trees). The RFR hyperparameter configuration obtained following the methodology exposed is listed in Table 11.

The accuracy of the model with the architecture described is shown in Table 9 where it can be observed that the predictive capabilities of the RFR model improve all the previous models. The best predictive capabilities are reflected in the accuracy metrics (R^2 and RMSE), where R^2 is the third highest value of all the models (0.70 vs 0.72 and 0.76), indicating a good fit between real and predicted values; while RMSE, as the main parameter considered for comparison of model improvement, is the lowest among all the models (RMSE = 36), indicating that the mean error average for the predicted values is the smallest. Figure S4 from Extended data¹⁶ shows how well the predictive values represent the real ones. As an additional application, the RFR allows obtaining the degree of importance of each input variable to the model. In this case, it was found that for the dataset created, chloride deposition was the most relevant feature in the prediction of corrosion (Figure S5 from Extended data¹⁶). This result is consistent with the earlier ANOVA analysis, where chloride deposition exhibited the highest sum of squares, confirming its dominant effect on corrosion rate variability. The convergence between the statistical (ANOVA) and machine learning (RFR) approaches reinforces the robustness of this finding. The high feature importance assigned to chloride deposition reflects its well-established physical significance in corrosion processes, particularly in marine and coastal environments. Therefore, its strong predictive power within the RFR model not only validates existing corrosion science but also demonstrates the model's ability to capture key environmental drivers without explicit mechanistic constraints.

Table 11. Best fit values of the hyperparameters adjusted for the random forest regressor (RFR) model.

Hyperparameter	Best fit value
Maximum depth	15
Minimum number of samples	6
Number of estimators	30

For the SVR model, the gridsearch algorithm was ran only for 5 times due to the high computational times required for each run. Once the best fit values of the hyperparameters were found (Table 12), the metrics from the best values fitted were obtained and summarized in Table 9. In this case, the SVR model fits the training data (R^2 training = 0.79) worse than the RFR model (R^2 training = 0.89), but the predictive capabilities are better as shown by the better fit of the validation data (R^2 validation = 0.72 for SVR and R^2 validation = 0.70 for RFR). Figure S6 shows the adjustment between real and predicted values.

The last ML model tested was MLPR. In this case, as mentioned in methodology section, the computational time was so high for evaluating multiple times the best configuration applying the gridsearch algorithm. Having in mind that, the gridsearch algorithm was employed once (without iterating each time the algorithm with a new random dataset splitting as before). Once the model architecture was decided (Table 13), the MLPR was trained and validated with the chosen hyperparameters.

The metrics obtained from the MLPR simulation are described in Table 9. The accuracy of the MLPR model for predicting corrosion values was the highest among the tested ML algorithms (R^2 validation = 0.76) but the error obtained is slightly higher than that obtained with SVR model (RMSE validation = 41 for MLPR and RMSE validation = 39 for SVR) as can be observed graphically in Figure S7 from Extended data¹⁶, where a comparison between predicted and real values is displayed. The figure shows that, despite the generally good correlation observed, a noticeable dispersion exists in some points at mid-to-high corrosion rates. Two main related factors may explain this behavior: firstly, a reduced number of samples are available for this high corrosion ranges, especially at C5 and CX, making it harder to accurately train the model. Secondly, MLPR is a relatively complex algorithm that tends to overfit the present trends when there is scarcity of data, which is particularly the case at high corrosion. The combination of these two factors may explain why other models, theoretically more limited, showcase better results and also suggests that there is still potential for this algorithm to improve when more corrosion data are available.

3.2.2 Analysis of models' accuracy metrics

Table 9 summarizes the main characteristics of each of the developed ML models, as well as the computational times that

Table 12. Best fit values of the hyperparameters adjusted for the support vector regressor (SVR) model.

Hyperparameter	Best fit value
Kernel	rbf
C	6.00
Gamma	3.40
Epsilon	0.03

Table 13. Best fit values of the hyperparameters adjusted for the multi-layer perceptron regressor (MLPR) model.

Hyperparameter	Best fit value
Activation function	relu
Learning rate	constant
Alpha	0.061
Solver	lbfgs
Hidden layers	(18,50,24)

have been carried out each time any of them was evaluated. The results show that the algorithm that captures the overall trend in the data more effectively is MLPR (R^2 validation = 0.76), although the error produced is slightly higher than SVR and RFR ($RMSE$ validation = 41 for MLPR, $RMSE$ validation = 36 for RFR and $RMSE$ validation = 39 for SVR) indicating that is not the most precise model minimizing the prediction error. The ability of the RFR model to aggregate the results of multiple decision trees helped it strike a balance between fitting the training data and generalizing to the validation set resulting in the lowest prediction error when compared with the other two (SVR and MLPR). Additionally, it can be observed how the computational analysis time of each of the algorithms increased as they become more complex.

Regarding computational time, although RFR, SVR, and MLPR produced similar levels of predictive accuracy, their computational demand differed. Among them, RFR was the most efficient timewise, giving stable results with shorter training times and minimal parameter adjustment. SVR and MLPR required considerably more processing time, mainly due to their iterative optimization and sensitivity to parameter settings. The training of MLPR, in particular, became more time-consuming for larger datasets or when frequent model updates were needed. Given that their predictive accuracy was comparable, computational efficiency becomes an important consideration for practical use. In this respect, RFR offers a good compromise between performance and computational

cost, while SVR and MLPR may be preferred only when their greater capacity to capture complex non-linear behavior provides a clear benefit.

3.3 Comparison with existing models

The collected data was used for calibrating existing corrosion models to compare if the ML model improves the models' behavior. Two models were tested with the full dataset built for the ML algorithm. The first one was the model of ISO 9224¹⁷ that follows the following relationship:

$$D = r_{corr} t^h \quad (5)$$

Where D is the CR in μm , r_{corr} is the corrosion rate experienced for each environmental case in the first year expressed in $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$, t is the time of exposure expressed in years and h is the metal-environment-specific time exponent calculated according to ISO 9224.

The h value obtained for the full dataset was 0.523, while a specific r_{corr} value was calculated for each dataset row. The accuracy metrics of the model were $R^2 = -0.13$ and $RMSE = 80$. Seeing these results, it can be concluded that this model has not predictive behavior with the current dataset, and it just can be applied in specific conditions where the range of the values is more limited than in the present dataset.

The second model that was tested was the Klimesmith's model³⁹. In this model, the following corrosion relationship is adjusted through the least-squares method⁴⁰:

$$y = A \cdot t^B \cdot \left(\frac{TOW}{C}\right)^D \cdot \left(1 + \frac{SO_2}{E}\right)^F \cdot \left(1 + \frac{Cl^-}{G}\right)^H \cdot e^{J \cdot (T+T_0)} \quad (6)$$

Where y is the CR in μm ; C , E , G and T_0 are the mean of each environmental parameter associated with. A , B , D , F , H and J are obtained from the least-squares method.

C , E , G and T_0 values were 3862.11, 21.54, 32.52 and 13.93, respectively. In the case of A , B , D , F , H and J , the values obtained employing the least-squares method were 9.81, 0.58, 0.57, 0.44, 0.51 and 0.033, respectively. With all the parameters found, the accuracy metrics of the Klimesmith's model were $R^2 = 0.6$ and $RMSE = 47.$, which are similar to the validation accuracy metrics obtained for the PR model ($R^2 = 0.61$, $RMSE = 46$). The Klimesmith's model can predict corrosion behavior, but it is a less powerful tool in comparison to the four best ML models (DTR, RFR, SVR and MLPR), which have better predictive capabilities than conventional models (see Table 9).

4 Conclusions

In this work, we have explored various levels of ML algorithms to address the problem of atmospheric corrosion considering environmental parameters, in order to determine which of the models offers the best predictive capabilities. Starting with

simpler models and progressing to more complex ones, RFR, SVR, and MLPR exhibited the best performance, with very similar accuracy metrics. Any of these models can reliably predict corrosion scenarios for environments ranging from C1 to C4 (which comprise the majority of the data) as well as C5-CX, though a higher dispersion has been observed in this last range as they only represent 12% of the dataset. The limited availability of data for C5-CX scenarios made these more challenging to model, especially for the most complex algorithms, and this has been identified as a limitation of the present study. With a view to future works, recent advances in data augmentation and transfer learning are techniques obtaining promising results and are proposed for addressing the challenges derived from data scarcity⁴¹.

Additionally, the RFR model revealed the importance of the environmental parameters on the corrosion behavior, being Cl⁻ deposition the most influential parameter in severe corrosion. This explains why offshore environments, where Cl⁻ is more prevalent, experience more intense corrosion compared to onshore environments, where Cl⁻ levels are lower.

Moreover, through an extensive literature review, we have compiled a comprehensive and curated dataset containing over 800 records of atmospheric steel corrosion under various environmental conditions, including T, TOW, SO₂ deposition rate, Cl⁻ deposition rate and exposure duration.

Data availability

Restricted data access statement

Data sets that are not publicly available are not present in any form in the manuscript. The publications from where the dataset's data was obtained are under subscription. Journal policies restrict the publication of its data, not its use in the

study. For granted access to the dataset data, subscription payment is required.

The dataset built for the study in [Subsection 2.1.2 Construction of the Dataset](#) was fully described on it to allow readers to identify data sets as similar to the analysis data as possible.

Underlying data

Zenodo: Development and Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms for Predictive Atmospheric Corrosion Modeling: Extended Data¹⁶.

The project contains the following underlying data:

1. [Extended data.docx](#)

Data are available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

Author contributions

The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: Lila Otero-Gonzalez, Jose Manuel Perales; data collection: Jose Manuel Perales Fernández; analysis and interpretation of results: Jose Manuel Perales Fernández, Lila Otero-Gonzalez; draft manuscript preparation: Jose Manuel Perales Fernández. Arturo Sánchez-Ramos, Maria Lopez Abelairas, Lila Otero-Gonzalez. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ✓ ?

Version 2

Reviewer Report 03 February 2026

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Zhongheng Fu

University of Science and Technology Beijing, Beijing, Beijing, China

The authors have carefully addressed the comments raised by the previous reviewers. Prior to publication, I recommend that the authors incorporate an interpretability analysis of the machine-learning results (e.g., feature importance or attribution analysis) to improve the transparency of the predictive model and enhance the appeal of the manuscript to readers in the corrosion science community.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Corrosion science, Machine learning

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 30 December 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.23871.r65333>

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Leonardo Bertolucci Coelho

Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium, Bruxelles, Belgium

Approved

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: corrosion, AI, machine learning

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Version 1

Reviewer Report 18 April 2025

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Leonardo Bertolucci Coelho

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Strengths:

- Comprehensive standardized dataset from diverse sources
- Systematic evaluation of multiple ML algorithms
- Clear methodology for model development and validation
- Practical focus on corrosion prediction
- Effective comparison with conventional models

Major Comments:

1. Literature Integration: Incorporate more recent peer-reviewed studies on ML for corrosion prediction, especially those related to similar conditions or methods.
2. Statistical Analysis: Add formal statistical tests (e.g., p-values or confidence intervals) to support model performance comparisons.
3. Performance at High Corrosion Rates: Directly address decreased accuracy at higher corrosion rates, discuss possible reasons, and suggest mitigation strategies relevant for offshore environments.
4. Dataset Limitations: Clearly state the limitation regarding low representation of C5-CX categories (12% of the dataset) and propose strategies for addressing this in future work.
5. Data Availability: Provide clearer details or justifications on dataset accessibility for reproducibility purposes.

Minor Comments:

- Correct typographical error "attempting methods" in Methods section.
- Expand discussion on RFR feature importance, particularly regarding chloride deposition.
- Ensure consistency in formatting tables and figures.
- Clarify dataset preprocessing steps, specifically handling of units and measurement methods.
- Include a brief discussion on computational efficiency for practical application.

Conclusion: The manuscript offers valuable insights into ML-based corrosion prediction. Addressing the suggested revisions, particularly statistical analysis, high corrosion rate performance, and literature integration, will significantly enhance its suitability for indexing.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: corrosion, AI, machine learning

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of

expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 26 Nov 2025

Arturo Sánchez-Ramos

Comment 1: We sincerely appreciate the constructive comments of the author. We have added the following references:

- For ML corrosion techniques: Moses, A., Peng, X., Wang, S. et al. Unraveling Magnesium Alloy Corrosion Patterns Through Unsupervised Machine Learning: Exploring Clustering Techniques for Enhanced Insight. JOM 76, 4388–4403 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-024-06674-4>.

- For Data Augmentation and Transfer Learning: Salma Fayaz, Syed Zubair Ahmad Shah, Nusrat Mohi ud din, Naillah Gul, Assif Assad, Advancements in Data Augmentation and Transfer Learning: A Comprehensive Survey to Address Data Scarcity Challenges, Recent Advances in Computer Science and Communications; Volume 17, Issue 8, Year 2024, e100124225452. DOI: [10.2174/0126662558286875231215054324](https://doi.org/10.2174/0126662558286875231215054324)

Comment 2: We have made an ANOVA analysis for the environmental parameters and how they affect corrosion, including p-values. The results of this analysis have been included in the revised version of the manuscript in Section 3.1, page 12.

Comment 3: Thank you for your constructive comment. Indeed, further discussion about the limitations of the model and the decreased accuracy at higher corrosion rates is needed. Two main reasons might be responsible for this observation: The first one is the lack of samples at the higher corrosion depths, making it harder for the algorithm to train properly at those ranges and resulting in less predictive accuracy. The second one, especially among the most complex algorithms, is related to the overfitting of the training dataset, which results in an overrepresentation of trends appearing in the training samples that are not followed outside that training sample. These two limitations have been discussed in the revised manuscript in Section 3.2 (evaluation of the models developed) and in Conclusions and some alternatives proposed for its mitigation in future works as commented in the next comment.

Comment 4: Following the previous comment, the lack of data samples in C5-CX categories has been discussed as a limitation found during the development of the present work. Data augmentation and transfer learning have been proposed as possible mitigation strategies to overcome this limitation for future works in Section 4 (page. 17).

Comment 5: We are committed to open science, but some of the data records were sourced from non-open access articles for which we do not have redistribution rights. For this reason, the dataset has not been published but replicability has been pursued as much as possible by indicating both the origin of the sources and the methodology followed for the subsequent data cleaning and preprocessing (Section 2.2).

Minor comments: The minor comments have been addressed following the indications of

the reviewer. We sincerely appreciate his attention to detail and constructive contribution.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 09 April 2025

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Atwakyire Moses

Kabale University, Kabale, Uganda

Comment: 1

The manuscript addresses relevant literature to some extent but would benefit from deeper integration of recent advancements in the field. In particular, the authors are encouraged to incorporate findings from the study published under Moses A et al. [2024 (Ref-1)] <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-024-06674-4>, which offers valuable insights that could enhance both the depth and contextual relevance of the current work. Additionally, the reference titled "*What is Corrosion? ECS, Accessed September 6, 2023*" is a general web source that lacks peer-review and scholarly rigor. Replacing it with the aforementioned peer-reviewed publication would improve the manuscript's credibility and better align it with academic standards.

Comment: 2

While the manuscript includes mean values and standard deviations for mechanical tests, the use of statistical significance testing (e.g., ANOVA or t-tests) is not explicitly mentioned. However, the trends are clear, and the interpretation is logical and backed by the data. If feasible, the inclusion of p-values or confidence intervals can strengthen the statistical robustness of the current work.

Comment 3

In the extended file data provided, The plot shows a general positive correlation between predicted and actual corrosion depths, indicating that the model captures the overall trend. However, there is a noticeable dispersion of data points around the best-fit line, particularly in the mid-to-high corrosion depth range. This suggests the model is less accurate when predicting higher corrosion levels. The presence of both under- and over-estimations (scattered points far from the line) reveals that prediction errors are not uniform across the range and these needs to be resolved.

Comment: 4

The conclusion is coherent and highlights both the practical implications of the findings and the contribution to the corrosion research community. However, the conclusion could be further strengthened by more explicitly addressing the limitations of the study (e.g., data scarcity) and suggesting how future work might overcome these. For example, strategies such as data

augmentation or transfer learning could be briefly mentioned. Additionally, while the provision of a publicly available dataset is available it does not provide the real dataset used in the manuscript, a more detailed mention of its potential applications (e.g., benchmarking future models or enabling domain-specific analysis) would reinforce its research value.

References

1. Moses A, Peng X, Wang S, Chen D: Unraveling Magnesium Alloy Corrosion Patterns Through Unsupervised Machine Learning: Exploring Clustering Techniques for Enhanced Insight. *JOM*. 2024; **76** (8): 4388-4403 [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Material science, Machine learning, corrosion Testing,

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 26 Nov 2025

Arturo Sánchez-Ramos

Comment 1: We thank the reviewer for this contribution. The reference to Moses et al. (2024) has been added to the introduction, as it provides valuable insights into corrosion pattern recognition using unsupervised machine learning. At the same time, we decided to retain the citation to the Electrochemical Society's overview [1], as it is a well-established scientific journal in the field and offers a concise and authoritative definition of corrosion.
Comment 2: We have made an ANOVA analysis for the environmental parameters and how they affect the corrosion, including p-values. The results of this analysis have been included

in the revised version of the manuscript in Section 3.1, page 12.

Comment 3: This is a very pertinent comment worth of further explanation on the paper. Two main reasons might be responsible for that observation: The first one is the lack of samples at the higher corrosion depths, making it harder for the algorithm to train properly at those ranges and resulting in less predictive accuracy. The second one, especially among the most complex algorithms, is related to the overfitting of the training dataset, which results in an overrepresentation of trends appearing in the training samples that are not followed outside that training sample. These two limitations have been discussed in the revised manuscript in Section 3.2 (evaluation of the models developed) and in Conclusions.

Comment 4: Following the suggestion from the previous and the present comment, the scarcity of data has been discussed in the conclusion section as a limitation found during the study. Data augmentation and transfer learning have been discussed as a way to overcome this current limitation in future works.

Regarding the dataset, while we are committed to open science, we regret that we cannot share the exact dataset used in this study due to the inclusion of samples from non-open access manuscripts for which we do not have redistribution rights. However, replicability has been pursued as much as possible by indicating both the origin of the sources and the methodology followed for the subsequent data cleaning and preprocessing (Section 2.2).

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
